

Chemistry of Bis-2'-Cyanoethyl Derivatives of some Aromatic Primary Amines: Part VI.* Preparation and Reactions of NN-Bis-2'-Cyanoethyl-*m*-Phenetidine

Km. V. Gupta and P. I. Ittyerah

NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-*m*-phenetidine (A) has been prepared. Nitrosation, bromination, tritylation and thiocyanation of this yielded the corresponding derivatives; the new group as expected entering para to the tertiary amino group. (A) on hydrolysis with alcoholic KOH and subsequent addition of conc. HCl gave NN-bis-2'-carboxyethyl-*m*-phenetidine.

In an earlier communication¹, the cyanoethylation of *m*-anisidine and some reactions of NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-*m*-anisidine were reported. This paper deals with the cyanoethylation and some reactions of the dicyanoethyl derivative. NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-*m*-phenetidine (A) has been prepared using the method recommended by Braunholtz and Mann².

On hydrolysis of (A) with alcoholic caustic potash and subsequent addition of excess of conc. HCl, the hydrochloride of NN-bis-2'-carboxyethyl-*m*-phenetidine (B) was obtained. Nitrosation of (A) in the usual manner gave a quantitative yield of NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-3-ethoxy-4-nitroso aniline (C; R = -NO) in green shining flakes and bromination using bromine in dioxane or bromine in glacial acetic acid yielded (C; R = -Br). Tritylation using triphenyl carbinol in presence of conc. HCl and thiocyanation using ammonium thiocyanate in presence of bromine and glacial acetic acid of (A) gave the *p*-trityl (C; R = -CPH₃) and the *p*-thiocyano (C; R = -SCN) derivatives respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-m-phenetidine.—(A): A mixture of *m*-phenetidine (5 g., 1 mol.), acrylonitrile (7.5 g., 3.5 mols.), glacial acetic acid (8 g., 3.5 mols.) and freshly prepared cuprous chloride (0.75 g.) was gently refluxed for 12 hr. The solution was then added with stirring

* Part V. *This Journal*.

1. O. P. Singhal, (Km) Veena Gupta and P. I. Ittyerah, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1966, 29, 69.
2. J. T. Braunholtz and F. G. Mann., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 3046.

to liquor ammonia (30 ml., 0.88 d.) and was kept overnight. The dark brown solid formed was filtered, washed well with water and dried. It was then recrystallised from ethanol. White shining flakes, yield 4.9 g. (55.3%), m.p. 87°, were obtained. (Found : N, 17.58%. $C_{14}H_{17}N_3O$ requires N, 17.28%).

NN-bis-2'-carboxyethyl-m-phenetidine hydrochloride : A mixture of 1 g., of *NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-m-phenetidine*, KOH (3 g.), ethanol (10 ml.) and water (20 ml.) was refluxed till no more ammonia was evolved. The solution was acidified with conc. HCl and the KCl formed was precipitated by the addition of acetone (50 ml.). After removing KCl the clear filtrate was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract after drying with $CaCl_2$ was evaporated to dryness when pale brown crystals of the hydrochloride were obtained, m.p. 190°. (Found : N, 4.21%; $C_{14}H_{20}NO_5Cl$ requires N, 4.41%).

NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-3-ethoxy-4-nitrosoaniline. (*C.R.* = -NO) : To an ice cold solution of 1 g. of (A) in conc. HCl (25 ml.) sodium nitrite (0.5 g.) dissolved in water (10 ml.) was added drop by drop until the colour of the solution became reddish brown. It was then made alkaline with caustic soda. Green flakes of *NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-3-ethoxy-4-nitrosoaniline*, yield 95.2%, m.p. 185–186° were obtained. This could be recrystallised from ethanol. (Found : N, 20.32%, $C_{14}H_{16}N_4O_2$ requires N, 20.58%)

NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-3-ethoxy-4-bromoaniline, (*C.R.* = -Br) : A solution of bromine (1.6 g.) in dioxane (16 ml.) was added slowly with stirring to a suspension of 2 g., of (A) in an aqueous solution of KOH (0.6 g. dissolved in 2 ml. water). This was then kept for an hour and the temperature was not allowed to rise above 5°. Dioxane was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue taken up in hot aq. ethanol. On cooling white crystals of the bromo compound, yield 2.5 g. (94.3%), were obtained. Recrystallisation from ethanol gave almost colourless crystals, m.p. 93–94°. (Found : N, 12.56%, $C_{14}H_{16}N_3BrO$ requires N, 13.04%).

NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-3-ethoxy-4-thiocyanoaniline, (*C.R.* = -SCN) : Bromine (0.5 ml.) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml.) was added dropwise with stirring to a mixture of 2 g. of (A) and ammonium thiocyanate (2 g.) in glacial acetic acid (38 ml.). The temperature was maintained below 20°. On addition of water (200 ml.), the product was precipitated and on recrystallisation from ethanol, white needles of the thiocyno derivative, yield 2.37 g. (96.6%), m.p. 127–128°, were obtained. (Found : S, 10.93%; $C_{15}H_{16}N_4OS$ requires S, 10.66%).

NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-3-ethoxy-4-triphenyl methyl aniline, (*C*; *R* = -CPR₃) : A mixture of 0.3 g. of (A) triphenyl carbinol (0.45 g.), acetic acid (5 ml.) and conc. HCl (0.2 ml) was refluxed gently for 3 hr. It was then diluted with water (100 ml.), basified with caustic soda, and left overnight. The product was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, yield 0.2 g. (34.5%), m.p., 190°. (Found : N, 9.34%; $C_{32}H_{31}N_3O$ requires N, 8.9%).

The authors are grateful to the Principal, St John's College, Agra, for providing necessary facilities.